

**DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF AN AUTOMATED PARKING
LOT ALLOCATION AND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FOR
RESERVED PARKING LOTS**

BY

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this study titled "**Design and Implementation of An Automated Parking Lot Allocation and Management System for Reserved Parking Lots**" is a bona fide work carried out by **Ekweanua Chiemerie David (16CH021493)** and was supervised by me and submitted to the Department of Computer and Information Sciences, College of Science and Technology, Covenant University, Ota.

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DEDICATION

This dissertation first is dedicated to God, who started the study with me and saw me through all till the end. It is also dedicated to my Father, Mr Ekweanua David, and my Mother, Mrs. Ekweanua Jane.

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First and most of all, I express my profound gratitude to God for the grace to start and conclude this study.

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ABSTRACT

Parking has been a necessity since the invention of vehicles and with massive increase of vehicles in today's society, easily locating an available parking space has become an ever-rising problem for the mass. The average individual spends a great deal of time locating an available parking slot in an unfamiliar or overcrowded parking lot. The inability of motorists to find ample parking spaces quickly and easily has led to a series of problems such as traffic congestion in the parking lots, illegal parking, environmental pollutions and so on. The objective of this study is to develop an inclusive parking allocation system for allocating vacant parking spaces to motorists. The methods used to in this study includes reviewing existing methods of parking allocation from contents on the web, and literature from journals studying articles, creation of use-case, activity diagram of the model, the model will be implemented with python language, PyQt5, MySQL lite.

Opark is a solution designed to remedy the problem. The implementation of this project will considerably increase the likelihood of vacant parking spaces being found thereby reducing the frustration of motorists unacquainted with the environment. It reduces the average journey time, energy use and air pollution. O-Park is one solution which is guaranteed to make the paring process easier.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND INFORMATION

The ease and expense of parking in a car park is crucial to deciding whether or not people want to travel to a certain location and whether or not they want to buy a vehicle. Focus is being placed on the ease of motorists in locating a vacant parking space and the ability to control the duration a motorist occupies a particular parking space so that more parking spaces will be available to other motorists. Good parking outcomes emphasize the application and integration of parking control.

According to (Malaysian Ministry of Transportation, 2007), 2006 recorded 458,293 recently registered vehicles relative to 1999 with only 296,716 existing registered vehicles, making an estimated rise of 54.5 million vehicles over 7 years. This signifies that there is an influx of vehicles and small parking spaces. Most parking lots are manually operated by humans (gatemen or security men), who do not possess the ability to track the number of vehicles that enter and leave the premises; they also cannot identify the number of parking spaces are free and their location. The motorist must proceed to circulate the car parking lot to locate the vacant space which adds to time wastage, not to mention the driver's anxiety and frustration. Many people are of the rather erroneous view that parking management is not crucial in building of facilities. Car parking is both relevant at municipal and regional planning stages. Car parking is a crucial aspect to be looked into when building any facility. It is one of the main issues throughout the project preparation and construction. It leads to pollution and breaches of laws, collisions and damages, time and money wasted if overlooked. Inability to find ample parking spaces may cause motorists to park illegally, Behrendt (1940) emphasized the tendency of the motorists to park as close as possible to their target which enhances cruising and also encourages them to utilize on-board or illegal parking. Over the years many manual approaches which include; shared parking, manual searching for free parking spaces and so on, have been employed to manage the parking process of motorists. However, due to

the randomness and inefficiencies of the current parking approaches, the aforementioned manual methods may be tapered off, for example, in a university that has many motorists entering and exiting the premises, it is physically impossible for the gatemen to ascertain the exact parking space that is not occupied by a vehicle hence the need for a parking allocation approach that takes into consideration the varying levels of traffic and is able to assign parking spaces that have not been occupied thereby promoting a fair and less chaotic parking environment.

Studies find that the product of drivers looking for a parking spot is 30% of traffic congestion (Gautam, 2019); this shows that a large amount of traffic will arise even in a limited time when searching for a parking spot, this problem in parking districts is a result of information regarding vacant parking areas is not easily available to the people searching for parking spaces. The conclusion that meets motorists is the possibility that there are no vacant parking spaces available. The traffic that arises from locating a parking spot may lead to an increase in environmental pollution. Slow-moving cars and cars at standstill emit more carbon monoxide to the environment, increasing environmental pollution. Parking allocation systems are needed mainly for large parking lots that has a large influx of vehicles, in terms of transport, demand is computed by behavior observation: for example, traffic movements or parking operations on a road. If the space available is equivalent or higher than the request, then output is comparable to the input report. Diaphanous analyses of parking demand models were carried out for various situations and specific circumstances from various cities around the world with different parking behavioral features. Emphasis is on examining in recent decades the development of parking models as well as research on parking behavior and parking characteristics. In the last several years the research on parking allocation has undergone a broad variety of approaches. Popular features in most surveys are parking costs, driving distance and travel time, but these considerations only affect the behavior of car parks in a variety of localities in various regions (Robert, 2000). Parking allocation systems are systems that handle the assignment of parking spaces in parking lots, it ensures that a space is vacant and guides motorists to a vacant parking space thereby reducing the stress faced by motorists in finding parking spaces, it also reduces environmental pollutions. It is mostly used in large parking lots.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Facilities are heavily vested in optimizing parking processes in parking lots to ease the parking process of motorists and also to generate revenue, with the emergence of modern facilities there is an increase in the number of people that visit these facilities. These facilities such as corporate center, shopping malls, hotels, supermarkets, residential buildings, government offices, schools and so on, must discover various ways to handle customer influx and their parking needs. The inability of motorists to find ample parking spaces quickly and easily has led to a series of problems such as traffic congestion in the parking lots, illegal parking, environmental pollutions and so on.

Existing platforms such as Arvio.com; neither include special allocation of parking spaces to handicap or trucks.

Hence, the need for a platform that recognizes the need to allocate special spaces for handicapped motorists and trucks.

1.3 AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To develop an inclusive parking allocation system for allocating vacant parking spaces to motorists.

- i. To review existing methods of allocation parking spaces in parking lots.
- ii. To design a model for parking allocation based on a modified algorithm derived from existing algorithms
- iii. To implement the model for inclusive parking allocation approach as a proof of concept prototype and demonstrate the efficiency and scalability of the prototype

1.4 METHODOLOGY

- i. A review existing methods of parking allocation from contents on the web, and literature from journals studying articles.
- ii. Creation of use-case, activity diagram of the model.
- iii. The model will be implemented with python language, PyQt5, MySQL lite.

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The implementation of this project will considerably increase the likelihood of vacant parking spaces being found thereby reduces the frustration of motorists unacquainted with the environment. It reduces the average journey time, energy use and air pollution. This system will increase the flow of movement in a parking lot as motorists know exactly where to go.

Facilities such as shopping malls, churches and so on, will also benefit from this project. People tend to avoid places that possess great difficulty in parking, this system improves the ease of parking thereby attracting more visitors to these facilities, granting these facilities more customers and finally a northward movement of the institutions' revenue.

1.6 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- i.** Car Security: No real measure to ensure the safety of vehicles parked in the parking lot.
- ii.** No accommodation was made for two-wheeled vehicles.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter gives an overview of some of the literature reviewed to identify relevant studies and support. This chapter also reviewed existing systems and their features.

2.2 OVERVIEW OF PARKING ALLOCATION SYSTEMS

Different fields of study have arisen as scholars conduct in-depth work into Parking allocation in parking lots. For example, some social researchers have concentrated on ways in which functioning in the parking lot helps to increase efficiency.

Parking allocation systems are systems that manage parking spaces in the parking lot, it can automatically assign an empty parking space to a vehicle, it is also able to make inclusion for different types of motorists from handicapped motorists to truck drivers eventually maintaining order in the parking lot.

Segun & Shoewu (2013) defined parking lot allocation system as a system that manages the entrance and exit to the building, tracks the spaces available in the parking lot, clearly allocates storage, detects an empty parking spot automatically, shuts down the system when all spaces are used, and can also be managed and monitored from a control center. According to Segun & Shoewu (2013), it is necessary for parking allocation systems in parking lots not to only focus on the entrance and exit of cars to a building, but the system should be able to manage available spaces in the parking lot, automatically assigning cars to them.

Idris, Leng, Tamil, Noor, & Razak (2009) proposed that parking lot allocation systems are systems that allows patrons to conveniently find, access and protect an empty parking area and any parking area that they feel convenient. According to Idris et al. (2009) emphasis is placed on the need for vehicle detection, as it plays a crucial role in the identification of cars.

Robert (2000) described a parking allocation system as a framework that includes some wireless communicators that can access a database over the Internet as well as parking information request to a wireless communication device over the internet. The wireless communication system can provide significant real-time representation of the parking data, showing the occupancy of the parking lot that is open. The occupancy condition changes in the available parking lot, depending on the presence and absence of vacant parking spaces (Robert, 2000).

Dušan & Panta (2006) proposed that the "intelligent" parking allocation control system is based on a combination of fuzzy reason and integer programming technique which determines online whether a new driver's parking request is acceptable or rejected. This definition gives a perspective on the presence of artificial intelligence in the system, as the system is able to determine through a set of already programmed measures to be followed to determine if a motorist should enter or not.

Parmar, Das & Dave (2020) defined parking allocation systems as a solution that rose to solve the chaos in parking lots because of motorists need to park as close as possible to their destination. They defined parking allocation systems as systems that are able to assign a parking space to motorists and charge them following prescribed parking policies.

Mario, Edouard, & Gold (2012) asserts that parking lot and allocation system tracks and gives information about the amount of free parking spaces, ensures safe use, navigates individual users to reserved parking spaces or parking spaces nearest to the final destination, and ensures correct payment by the time the vehicle spent on the parking space. In order to inform drivers of the number of free car parks and their division across various parking lots or across different levels in specific parking spots, driver information systems are based on technologies developed within the Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) (Mario, Edouard, & Gold, 2012).

2.2.1 History of Parking Lot

Parking lots are cleared spaces for the parking of vehicles. Ben-Joseph (2019) proposed that as long as cars exist there will forever be need for parking lots. They are areas that are necessary for the parking of cars and organizing cars. Artist Mitchell

(1970) complains in her song “big yellow taxi” that “They paved paradise and put up a parking lot.”, she views parking lots as polar opposite of nature's fields and forests, a grotesque example of our car-oriented society's costs. Author Ben-Joseph (2019) defined parking lots as much more than places to store cars temporarily, that they are public spaces that have a significant impact on the design of our cities and suburbs, the natural environment and the rhythms of everyday life. Hence parking lots have become integrated with our modern society even to the extent of becoming a necessity in order to reduce traffic and pollution.

Parking allocation systems have existed since before the invention of cars people used to manually look for where to tie their horses. Parking services and related technologies have expanded and diversified over the years. Since the moment vehicles were created, car parking structures have been around. There are car parking schemes in any place (school, church, bank) where there is a large volume of traffic.

The very first recognized transportation started in the 1400's ("The History of Parking Lots", 2015), this mainly involved the use of horses for transportation, as more people began riding horses there was an increased need for parking. Therefore, parking spaces were created, after the invention of the assembly line by Henry Ford in 1908, cars became more popular. More residents then got automobiles and there was a desire for parking lots ("The History of Parking Lots", 2015). Due to the extremely large sizes of the cars during that period diagonal parking was invented. Kale, et al. (2016) asserts that in the 1920s, throughout U.S. cities like Los Angeles, Chicago, New York and Cincinnati, precursors of automated parking systems emerged. For the Chicago Century of Progress Exhibition in 1933, the Nash Motor Company produced the first glass-closed version of this device and was the predecessor to a more recent version, the Smart Car Towers in Europe (Kale, et al., 2016). Compact cars then joined transport in the 1960s and 1970s. The parking lots

were smaller and more convenient along with the compact cars ("The History of Parking Lots", 2015). Parking became much simpler and closer to your destination. Existing multi-story buildings were modified for new applications. An art deco landmark that was converted into five luxury condos in 1983 is one of the Kent Automatic Parking Garages now known as Sofia Apartments (Kale, et al., 2016). Kale, et al. (2016) asserts that although interest in the Automated (car) parking system (APS) in United States (US.) languished until the 1990s, more technically advanced APS had been built since the 1970s by Europe, Asia, and Central America. Around 40,000 parking spaces were installed annually in the early 1990s using the Japanese paternoster APS. An additional 1,6 million APS parking spaces will be available in Japan in 2012 (Kale, et al., 2016).

2.3 PARADIGM SHIFT IN PARKING MANAGEMENT

Parking management is a conceptual shift, a revolution in the concept of parking issues and future solutions. Parking today in the 21st century has changed drastically from what it used to be in the previous era. With the introduction of various technologies parking has taken a huge leap from where it used to be (Curcio, 2017). In the old paradigm parking was manual, nothing was automated, motorists would move round the parking lot in search of available parking space, parking policy consists primarily of high minimum parking requirements, with indirect costs imposed by taxation and leasing. In the new paradigm involves technology, as it is the main driving force in the new age parking. Parking facilities are widely used, and parking lots can often be filled (usually more than once a week) at a location, but alternative options are available in the vicinity, and passengers have knowledge of these options.

Technology is the engine of the parking industry and the customers who use it are evolving and growing as accessible infrastructure continues to grow. According to a survey conducted by IPI (2012), the installed worldwide smart car park base is anticipated to hit 1.1 million by 2026, technology is consistently reshaping the ever-changing parking industry. There is no one technology for anything. We have a variety of different parking technology used by city officials and parking operators to help make the parking industry more efficient, more productive and sustainable. In recent years the smart parking industry has experienced a substantial change. Several big, high-profile installations,

including in Moscow, San Francisco and Los Angeles, were typical of the early stages of the intelligent parking ventures (Curcio, 2017). While these schemes were effective in decreasing pollution and traffic in parking lots, it has proven impossible to secure the requisite funds for schemes with a similar scale. Therefore, the average project size has dropped, even as the number of projects has risen (especially for smaller cities). In the future, the introduction of autonomous vehicles (AVs) will have a huge effect on the smart parks sector, several cities around the world are now beginning to study vehicles for self-parking, professional AV car parks and autonomous car parks valets.

2.3.1 Characteristics of Parking

Data on parking accessible space should be given at the initial stage of the analysis in order to take efficient steps towards fostering parking conditions to the degree that it is utilized, the length of parking spaces, the estimation of parking requests, and so on. Various studies of the parking attributes or figures are performed in order to extract various characteristics. These different car park features are used to test and assess the adequacy and reliability of current parking areas or lots. It provides an overview into the duration of the car park. The accumulation profiles are available for testing of market models. The following car parking features are commonly used;

- i. Parking accumulation: This is the cumulative number of vehicles stored at the specified time period. The graph called the accumulation curve, or profile, is usually depicted by the circle. It displays the increases in parking accumulation over a defined time or survey duration in a given parking facility (Tong, Wong & Leung, 2004). They built a technique for calculating the aggregation profile of parking spaces during the day, by utilizing parking surveys and cluster analyses.
- ii. Parking volume: This is the cumulative number of parking vehicles for a given time span or measurement span (Parmar, Das & Dave, 2020). In this the reuse of the same vehicle will not be taken into account. The number of automobiles accessed during the survey time was then only recorded. (Parmar, Das & Dave, 2020).

- iii. Capacity: This is the cumulative amount of available parking space / inlets on a single parking lot (Parmar, Das & Dave, 2020).
- iv. The number of vehicles registered at a given period, e.g., the space break aggregation, is the occupancy factor or parking index for the same car park. The load is often separated by the power for a certain time period. The efficient usage of the car park is a test of the capacity (Tong, Wong & Leung, 2004).
- v. Kanani (2017) described parking load as the cumulative region below the accumulation curve. It is normally accomplished by the calculation of the number for this span of time of the automobiles occupying parking space. It is represented as hours of the engine.
- vi. The cumulative number of automobiles registered over the whole sample duration shall be separated by the average parking time. Often, all vehicles separated by the number of vehicles stored during the survey duration can be calculated as the amount of parking time.
- vii. Parking turnover: This is the product of distinguishing between the total number of registered vehicles for the whole sample span and the total amount of usable parking spaces (Parmar, Das & Dave, 2020). There is a certain amount of space reserved for each of the parking areas on the car park. It offers an analysis of the total number of cars parking in each car park. This can be expressed by time per bay as the number of vehicles.
- viii. Peak parking saturation: This is the number of vehicles parked at peak time to the total number of parking space available (Chen, Wang & Pan, 2016).
- ix. The peak ratio of parking: This is the ratio reached by the splitting number of parked vehicles with the total number of parked vehicles at each interval (Mimbela & Klein, 2007).

2.3.2 Types of Parking Choice

It is important to consider how drivers may select their parking choice to determine car parking pricing strategies and parking allocation details. Chaniotakis & Pel (2015) emphasized the importance of identifying how drivers cope with issues regarding the quest periods involved to locate an empty parking spot. There are two types of parking decision namely;

- i. On Street Parking: This parking is a form of parking which comprises all parking spaces alongside the path (Asiyanbola & Akinpelu, 2012). On-street parking is regarded as the closest route to the destination and is the product of a shortage of room for off-street parking. On-street parking or pavement parking is in an empty area. There are cases of fines being charged for each parking area filled. Fined parking on-street appears to be secure else it is dangerous (Asiyanbola & Akinpelu, 2012). The on-street parking is accessible in two ways, the approved and the unofficial. On-street official parking comprises of parking facilities, municipal parking facilities, social parking facilities, business car parks, entertainment and media parking lots. Non-official on-street parking is, however, named curbs, because of its location nearby. These comprise shopping malls, business parks and so on. On street parking decision process can be seen below.

Figure 2.1 On-street parking choice process figure

(Source: warden.com)

- ii. Off-Street Parking: This ensures you park your car somewhere but, on the sidewalks, (Asiyanbola & Akinpelu, 2012). Typically, they are parking areas and garages. Off-street parking maybe indoors or outdoors. Private properties, garages, and driveways often provide off-street car parking. On-street car park customers are frequent drivers who utilize the area for a short time. Payers of off-street parking vary from short and long-term drivers, for example daily visitors and frequent payers. The parking process in off-street parking is displayed below.

Figure 2.2 Off-street parking choice process

(Source: warden.com)

2.3.3 Types of Parking Bay

Parking bay applies to any region of parking space offered for the departure of a vehicle and identified on the parking lot surface. The parking bays in the United States and Nigeria typically have a total range of 8.5 - 9.0 feet (2.6 – 2.7 meters) (Chen, Wang & Pan, 2016). Angled, perpendicular spaces may be needed to unlock doors, whereas parallel parking spots on low-traffic residential streets might be narrower, throughout building, different considerations decide the precise dimensions of a parking area ("Online TDM Encyclopedia - Parking Solutions", 2020). This implies a high land cost would encourage smaller measurements and the creation of compact areas but low land cost would encourage larger parking bay measurements. There are different forms of parking bays:

Parallel parking bay: This is a primary parking bay commonly used in on-street parking. In this, the front bumper of a vehicle is placed along the line facing the rear bumper of a neighboring one (Chaniotakis & Pel, 2015). When one is provided, this

is carried out in addition to a curb. It may also be found in road parks and public parks, typically only in comparison to the parking areas used in other types.

Perpendicular parking bay: The cars are situated side by side, perpendicular to the lane, curb, or street, as well as the bay space (Asiyanbola & Akinpelu, 2012). This kind of parking is seen in public parks and street parks with more cars per length of the path (or curb) than parallel parking.

Angle parking: Angle parking is identical to perpendicular parking in that the vehicles are situated at an angle to the corner of the nave (a steep angle with a view) (Chaniotakis & Pel, 2015). The smoother change makes parking easier and faster, wider aisles and thus better width than perpendicular parking. While the aisles are theory one way, they are usually sufficiently large to allow two cars to move slowly if drivers go the wrong way down the aisles.

Tandem parking bay: This is commonly associated for automobile parking in suburban neighborhoods, in which two motor cars park nose to tail in conjunction (Chaniotakis & Pel, 2015). For the first car there is no direct access and in the second vehicle access needs to be given

Handicap parking bay: This is a parking bay that is dedicated to people with disabilities. Disabled car parks are usually labelled with the International Access Logo, but the configuration of the logo is somewhat specific in reality (Mimbela & Klein, 2007). Most Nigerian parking lots do not possess a handicapped parking bay (Mimbela & Klein, 2007). The prime purpose of the parking area for disabled people is to guarantee the entry and exit of those with disabilities for secure, accessible and convenient parking. These persons might have walking sticks, walkers or crutches, they require more room than usual parking areas for secure service. Any disability parking lot needs to be seen with blue painted contours and designated signage that say 'Parking by a Disability Only.' In fact, certain states allow a wheelchair-bound stick figure on the pavement within the slot.

Figure 2.3 Handicap Parking Bay

(Source: pavement.com)

2.3.4 Reasons for a Parking Allocation System

This section reviews some reasons that prompted the need for Parking Allocation Systems (P.A.S).

- i. Locate a parking space quickly: This is one of the most prominent reasons for developing a parking allocation system. Motorists often find it difficult to locate a free parking space and may be forced to circulate the parking lot in search if any available parking space, this may lead to them parking illegally and has the tendency of increasing the frustration of the motorist. P.A.S makes this process easy as it automatically locates an available parking space and guides motorists to their location.
- ii. Reduce Traffic Congestion: IPI (2012) reported that at any given time approximately 30 percent of a city's vehicles contribute to traffic because motorists are searching for space. Such vehicles create traffic chaos apart from the annoyance element, perceived by other drivers. It translates into incalculable levels of excess gas and carbon emissions from an ecological point of view (IPI,2012). Because of a lack of parking facilities in a business, vehicle owners park on a street lining the paths. This can cause pedestrians to walk on the side of the road leading to an obstruction in the free movement of vehicles thereby

causing traffic. The P.A.S eradicates this problem by making the location of parking spaces easy and smoothening the parking process reducing traffic or congestion

- iii. Reducing Pollution: Studies find that the product of drivers looking for a parking spot is 30% of traffic congestion (Gautam, 2019). High speed vehicles emit fewer pollutants but traffic jams become the order of the day due to lack of space. Therefore, pollutants are released more strongly as most motorists leave their engines on when they're stuck in traffic, which is often triggered by people looking to park (Gautam, 2019). Studies have shown that our life span is influenced by the air we breathe, these vehicles as they move slowly through the parking lot looking for space, their carbon emission increases, polluting the air which eventually affects our life span, P.A.S eradicates this problem by making movement flow easily in the parking lots, eradicating the need for vehicles to be at a standstill in traffic.

2.4 REVIEW OF EXISTING SYSTEMS

This section contains the review, features and challenges of some systems that operate in the commitment contract scope including: Park Alto and Arvio

2.4.1 Park Alto

Park Alto: This is one of the leading smart parking management system, with a 5-star rating from captterra (an online platform that helps people to find the best business software's).

Figure 2.4 Park Alto

(Source: paralto.com)

Methodology used:

- The application that is developed using MATLAB
- ANPR (Automatic number plate recognition) systems

The key features of park alto include;

- Allows reservations to be made
- Total valet & parking network combined with leading barrier gate suppliers
- Mainly for airports
- Access Controls
- Easy & understandable UI

Limitations;

- It cannot be used across different platforms

2.4.2 Arivo

Arivo is working towards making parking management for office or residential buildings as a simple, safe & effective process. Encourage & provide staff & visitors with easy access to advanced allocation technologies.

Figure 2.5 Arvio Screenshot

(Source: Arvio.com)

Methodology used:

- Python & Raspberry pi is used for development
- Image capturing source
- Sensors & actuators
- ANPR systems

The key features of Arvio includes;

- Access Controls
- License plate recognition
- Reservations Management

Limitations:

- Not cross platform

Table 2.1 Comparison of existing system

Systems Reviewed	Comparative Features				
	Easy UI	Cross Platform	Reduces Traffic	Cost	Supports Different Vehicles (Trucks)
Park Alto	○	●	●	○	○
Arivo	●	○	●	●	○
Proposed System	●	●	●	●	●
● = Supported ○ = Not Supported					

CHAPTER THREE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

3.1 INTRODUCTION

System analysis means the process carried out in order to study the system and its components to determine its goals. It is a system-enhancing solution technique that ensures all of the system's components work effectively to fulfill their objectives. System analysis contributes to system development, performance enhancement and reaching productivity and growth goals (Jawahar, 2012). System analysis was performed on O-Park by specifying its functional and Non-functional requirements.

System design refers to the process of identifying, creating and implementing structures that fulfill a company or organization's unique needs and requirements. System design is the process of identifying the different components of a system and communicating with them in order to fulfill specified needs (Kendall & Kendall, 2011). O-Park has a logical design and a physical design.

3.2 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

System architecture is a general practice to treat artifacts known as systems (existing or envisioned) in a manner that promotes thought about their structural properties. According to (Golden, 2015). The design and structure of a parking allocation system includes the following:

- i. **Display Layer:** It's the environment where human-machine encounters take place. The aim of this relationship is to make it easier to run and manage the system effectively, while also providing the system with knowledge that lets operators make their decisions. This includes the components of the UI and the components of the application of the UI. The key objective of this layer is how end users will view the software. The right categories of customers who interact with the network are decided through this layer process. The GUI was developed using python's PyQt.

- ii. Logic layer: This is the environment where processing takes place, it is taken out of the display stage and monitors the functionalities of the program by a thorough analysis as its own layer. This level defines the whole architecture of the database, including the interaction between records, data schema. Within this stage of design, storage constraints and security are often enforced. DBA (database administrator) manages this standard.
- iii. Data Layer: This layer shows how data is saved in the storage devices. Space is also allocated to the data on this layer. This is architecture's lowest level. This layer comprises of the frameworks for data persistence (database servers, file pieces and so on) and the access layer which captures and stores the data. A table-based classification is used to create a simplified device data management system that can move data through frontier layers.

Figure 3.1 System architecture

3.2.1 Physical Design

Physical design is associated with the real device input and output. This concentrates on how data is accessed, checked, interpreted and presented as output in a system. The parking allocation system (Opark) will be deployed on a computer, which would be implemented using the application architecture. These components consist of the display layer, the data layer and the logic layer. The work framework of Opark is created by specifying the design specification, which defines precisely what the candidate method is doing. The user interface design, process design and data design are involved.

3.2.2 Input Design

This is the bridge between clients and the system. Input design deals with all the processes of inserting human information into the system, it deals with how information or data is entered into the system. It requires guidelines and protocols for data management and these measures may be done by reviewing the machine to interpret details from a published or typed record to ensure the transaction information is presented in a functional manner for analysis or by bringing users information or data directly to the system. The input design concentrates on the control of the information needed, the elimination of defects, delays, additional steps and reliability of the operation.

3.2.3 Output Design

Output design deals with all the processes of extracting information out the system to users, it deals with how information is presented to the user of the system. A standard output satisfies the end-user.

The users and other programs are notified by outputs of certain device performance.

During output design, the displacement of information and even hard copy performance is calculated. It is the key details for the customer and the most important source. Effective and smart output design strengthens the users to make decisions.

3.2.4 Logical Design

Conceptual design is an early step of the design phase, in which the general details of something's purpose and shape are organized. It encompasses interface architecture, interactions, procedures and techniques.

The logical design comprises of;

1. The Sign-up Module
2. The Login Module
3. The add a car module
4. The remove a car module
5. The view all available slots module

The logical module is represented:

Figure 3.2 Logical model

3.3 SYSTEM ANALYSIS

The system analysis for the O-Park application involves the collection and analysis done on various available facts, finding problems, and breaking down the system into its various components based on the identified problems. This analysis was carried out to analyse the system or its components and establish the system goals.

3.3.1 The Implemented System

The name of the system is O-Park. O-Park is a desktop application designed to solve the problem of parking allocation in parking lots, it assigns vehicles that enter a premise into a parking lot, it is able to assign vehicles based on the vehicle type, it also stores the time of entry and time of exit of the vehicle.

3.4 USER REQUIREMENTS

Requirement analysis is the process for evaluating system user preferences. Such characteristics known as specifications, need to be calculated, applicable and comprehensive. The operating framework specifications shall be categorized as functional and non-functional specifications and defined in relation to the parking application.

3.4.1 Functional Requirements

Functional requirements are features or functions which developers have to implement to allow users to perform their tasks, these requirements show who reads it what the program will do and the device actions in accordance with the functions of the system.

The limitations on the specifications have created several issues in software development, and this is particularly relevant for mobile devices since the design is a function of the consumer.

Below are the functional requirements for O-Park.

- i. The user shall be able to add a new vehicle to the lot
- ii. The user shall be able to remove a vehicle from the lot
- iii. The user shall be able to view the list of all vehicles that entered the premises
- iv. The user shall be able to specify the vehicle type (Truck or car)
- v. The system shall be able to assign lot space to a vehicle
- vi. An ID shall uniquely identify each vehicle in the system
- vii. The user shall be able to view the date and time the vehicle entered the premises
- viii. The user shall be able to view the date and time the vehicle left the parking lot premises

3.4.2 Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirement is an obligation specifying criteria that can be used instead of specific actions in assessing a system operation. They are opposed to functional requirements which define specific behaviour or functionality.

Non-functional specifications can be extracted from the required program functionality (product specifications), software development agencies (organized requirements) or external sources. Below are some non-functional requirements.

- 1) Understandable: The application should provide an easy and well specified user interface. Users should easily accomplish tasks. The buttons should be easily visible. One should be able to interact with the application easily. The colours of the application should be inviting.
- 2) Availability: The application should be ready for use 24/7. This implies that the program is expected to be operating at every moment. High-availability systems can record availability in terms of annual downtime minutes or hours.
- 3) Efficiency requirement: the program should allow reasonable and efficient usage of python resources, and the program should not fail. This should be such that memory and utilities do not impact the output of other programs in the network.
- 4) Privacy requirement: The data should be held private and should be kept safe against all suspicious and malicious threats.

3.5 SYSTEM DESIGN

The system design of the O-Park involves the graphical representation of the process and workflow of the entire system. System modelling is the method of designing abstract model systems, each of which has a different viewpoint of the system. System modeling helps the analyst to understand the system functionality and the models are employed for customer communication. They are processes by which models of a system can be analyzed to detect and understand the essence of the systems, giving us the ability to identify and equate the desired quality factors with the system requirements (Fleming, 2016).

This section presents different graphical models used to describe the Opark structure. There are two ways in which a system can be modelled namely; behavioral and structural models.

Behavioral models describe the internal dynamic aspects of an information system that supports an organization's business processes (Dennis, Wixom & Tegarden, 2012). In the

course of the study, behavioral models explain what the internal logic of the processes is without defining how to execute the processes. This section utilizes behavioral models such as use case diagrams and activity diagrams.

A structural or logical model defines the arrangement of the objects in an enterprise that enables business processes (Dennis, Wixom & Tegarden, 2012). During analysis the functional structure of objects is provided by the conceptual model without specifying how they are processed, generated or manipulated to allow researchers to concentrate on business without removing themselves from technical results. This section utilizes structural models such as the class diagram.

Behavioral and Structural models were both used to implement O-Park, the behavioral models implemented on O-Park includes use case diagrams and activity diagrams while the structural models used includes the class diagram.

3.5.1 Use-Case Models

A use-case model is a model of how various user types interact with the system to resolve a problem. Therefore, it explains the expectations of users, the user's experiences with the system and how the program operates to accomplish the purpose or specified objectives. A typical use-case diagram incorporates the following;

- I. Actors: It is a consistent set of roles played by users of cases when they communicate with these use-case models.
- II. Use-Case: A model element that shows each case of use. Properties include name of the case and case specification for use
- III. Associations: This is the connection between an individual and a use-case
- IV. Subject: A model component that constitutes the limit of the interest structure.
- V. Generalization: The term generalization refers to the relationship between two use-cases that shows that the composition, conduct, and relationship of a different actor (parent) is inherited from one use case (kid).
- VI. Dependencies: This is a widespread relationship describing the inclusion of the behaviour described in a different use case.

A use-case model can be used for the following;

- I. Used for the selection of device specifications.
- II. Determine the external and internal system variables.
- III. Show how the criteria and actors connect

Figure 3.3 Use-Case Model

The use case shown in figure 3.3 is explained thus:

- I. The user (Admin) logs in
- II. The user (Admin) is able to add a car
- III. The user (Admin) is able to make a place available by removing a car
- IV. The user (Admin) is able to specify the type of vehicle available (truck or car).
- V. The user (Admin) is able to print out the list of spots available
- VI. Finally, the user (Admin) is able to exit

Table 3.1 Use-Case workflow

ID	Activity	Primary Actor	Priority
1	Log in	User	High
2	Add car	User	Medium
3	Specify vehicle (truck or car)	User	Medium
4	Check spots available	User	Medium
5	Exit	User	Medium

3.5.2 Activity Diagrams

The activity diagram is essentially a framework that shows the flow from one activity to another. The control flow is drawn between the different operations. The activities diagram is basically an improved version of the flow map that models the interaction between activities. A typical activity diagram incorporates the following;

- I. Activity: The activity can be described as a system operation
- II. Action: It is a named entity that contains a particular atomic phase, in other words it does not decompose further in the operation.
- III. Control flow: Displays the execution process, it is in an arrow form.
- IV. Object flow: Show the movement of an entity from one operation to another activity.
- V. Decision node: Reflect a check condition for ensuring the control flow only goes one direction

Figure 3.4 Activity Diagram

3.5.3 Class Diagrams

A Unified Modeling Language (UML) class diagram is a type of static structural diagram which outlines the system structure by presenting the classes of the system, attributes, strategies and objects interrelationships. The generalization and the aggregation are two

important relations. The class name, attributes and operations are often shown in each class object in the diagram.

Figure 3.5 Class Diagram

3.6 PROCESS ARCHITECTURE

The process architecture refers to how the procedures and structures of a system are constructed hierarchically as the inputs through the outputs are converted. Oparks process architecture diagram shows us the structural design of the system. It describes the principles used by agents and stakeholders to identify and analyse the operations of a system. A process architecture basically comprises of three categories namely;

- i. Guiding process: These processes provides expectations, strategies, requirements and oversight of all other system processes. They are not the heart of the system rather they are the brain of the system. They are incredibly significant, even if they are not the core process. This can be viewed as a supporting group and one is needed for increasing leading or restricting principle or object to be handled. Activities under this category includes; processes for resolving plans, legislation, budgets, regulations and other concerns in the management.
- ii. Core process: These are cross-functional end-to-end system processes that deliver interest to potential clients or intermediaries directly. Core processes are also considered key processes because they reflect the basic tasks undertaken by an entity to accomplish its aims and priorities, serve its position and satisfy its beliefs. The key processes are those that include designing and producing a product or service, selling and delivering it to the consumer or user of the item and customer reviews or product or service after sales.
- iii. Enabling process: Enabling processes otherwise known as support processes are built to promote key processes with interest through the provision of primary process capital and services. A big distinction in support processes and core processes is that supporting processes provide value to existing consumers and not provide value directly to third-party consumers. Some examples of enabling processes includes; the delivery of IT, accounting and human resources facilities and the procurement of products and services to domestic clients.

Figure 3.6 Process architecture

3.7 DATABASE DESIGN

The Opark framework database has been developed utilizing MySQL, providing user-related information. This database includes related tables which show their data types and attributes. The following is the summary of the tables:

- i. Admin: This table contains the admin's information such as Username and password
- ii. Add vehicle: This table contains a detail of vehicles that entered into premises
- iii. Manage vehicle: This table contains a list of vehicles currently in the lot, from here a vehicle can be removed.
- iv. History: This table contains a list of all previous vehicles in a parking lot.

Table 3.2 Lot register

COLUMN NAME	DATA TYPE	SIZE
NAME	VARCHAR	50
VEHICLE NUMBER	INT	50
MOBILE	INT	11
VEHICLE TYPE	VARCHAR	50

Table 3.3 Admin

COLUMN NAME	DATA TYPE	SIZE
NAME	VARCHAR	50
PASSWORD	VARCHAR	50

Table 3.4 Manage Vehicles

COLUMN NAME	DATA TYPE	SIZE
ID	INT	12
NAME	VARCHAR	50
VEHICLE NUMBER	INT	50
MOBILE	INT	11
VEHICLE TYPE	VARCHAR	50
ENTRY TIME	DATE	

Table 3.5 History

COLUMN NAME	DATA TYPE	SIZE
ID	INT	12
NAME	VARCHAR	50
VEHICLE NUMBER	INT	50
MOBILE	INT	11
VEHICLE TYPE	VARCHAR	50
ENTRY TIME	DATE	
EXIT TIME	DATE	

CHAPTER FOUR

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The system implementation uses the architecture structure created and system analysis results to build system elements that meet the stakeholder needs and system requirements developed in the early phase of life cycles system implementation.

O-Park has been created with an easy to use interface This contains both technical elements and programming languages required to build the proposed framework. Images are used to illustrate device features and functions

4.2 SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

System requirements are the functionality a machine will provide to operate effectively and reliably with respect to a hardware or software program. Failure to fulfill these requirements may lead to problems of installation or performance.

These requirements are in place to ensure that O-Park runs efficiently and effectively, it helps to prevent O-park from not getting installed and prevent malfunction or the system performing below expectation or even to hang or crash.

Table 4.1 System Requirement

Requirement	Software
Operating system	Windows, Mac
Minimum SDK version	17
Database	SQL
Development tool	PyCharm
Programming language	PyQt

Table 4.2 Minimum Requirement

Software	Minimum Requirement
Windows 7,8,10	Screen size not more than 17 inches
Primary Memory	1GB RAM

Table 4.3 Recommended requirement

Recommended Requirement	Software
Operating System	Windows 10
Primary Memory	2GB RAM
Secondary Memory	5 GB hard drive

4.3 THE IMPLEMENTATION TOOLS USED

PyCharm is the resource that is used for program creation and implementation. PyCharm is the most common script IDE used in Python. PyCharm is equipped with many useful plugins for the development of your system. Some of the plugins used in the development of O-Park includes; PYQT5, MySQL.

PyQt is a toolkit for Interface widgets. This is a Python guide to Qt, one of the best and most common interconnecting GUI libraries. PyQt is a combination of Python and the Qt application programming language.

The MySQL Shell is a JavaScript, Python or SQL-interface console that helps MySQL Server creation and management, and is a MySQL Server feature. To execute data requests and modifications, as well as specific administrative tasks, you will use MySQL Shell.

4.4 SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT METHODOLOGIES

Software development methodologies are standardized methods of developing the system development life cycle (SDLC). Many organizations have their own methodologies perfected through the years, and the agile approach for growth is to be utilized for this project. Agile development is a community of programming-centered methodologies that

rely on the SDLC stream. The greatest benefit of agile development is that it allows teams to deliver output more rapidly, more effectively and reliably and to respond to change.

The aim is to generate usable applications rapidly using an agile approach. The agile growth method as demonstrated in Figure 12

Figure 4.1 Agile Methodology

Beck et al. first defined agile concepts and have developed since that period (Sommerville, 2011). The following concepts can be represented in a variety of terms like:

- i. Deliver to the client with functioning apps
- ii. When improvements are made late, they should be taken into consideration.
- iii. Providing operating devices not just slowly but also
- iv. Encourage investors and consultants to work closely on a regular basis
- v. Persons who are trust driven to do the job
- vi. face to face Dialogue is facilitated
- vii. The key emphasis is on making apps run.
- viii. The promotion of constant, routine and sustainable growth
- ix. Implement mobility with proper configuration
- x. Aid for self-organizing teams
- xi. Fast retrofit
- xii. Value is promoted
- xiii. Occasionally test and modify actions
- xiv. Approve simplification

4.5 THE PROGRAM MODULES AND INTERFACES

The framework comprises many modules which are mutually autonomous and the homepage gathers details from all these modules and presents it to the consumer for easy access in a condensed edition.

- i. Splash screen
- ii. Register parking system
- iii. Log-in
- iv. Home screen
- v. Add vehicle
- vi. Manage vehicle
- vii. History

4.5.1 The Splash Screen

The diagram in figure 4.2 is the splash screen, which is the first module the user sees once the application is launched. A splash screen is a visual control feature consisting of a

picture frame, an emblem and the latest app update. A splash screen is typically shown at the start of a game or program. A splash screen is an application's summary display.

Figure 4.2 Splash Screen

4.5.2 Register Parking System

This is the second module a new user sees on the application. The registration module is where admins can store their password and name, which will be used to access their accounts in the future. The registration portal (also known as a sign-up account) enables managers and entities to sign separately to view their O-park data. In this module admins can specify the number of lots they have assigned to four-wheel cars and sixteen-wheel

trucks. The module is very unique because each user or admin can be separated from their usernames and passwords and no two admins can have access to the same account. The diagram in figure 4.3 shows the registration module.

Figure 4.3 Register lot

4.5.3 The Login Module

The diagram in figure 4.4 shows the login module, this module handles security and identification of the user. In computer protection, log-in is the mechanism through which an individual achieves entry to his or her computer device by identification and authentication. User credentials are usually a type of "username" and a corresponding "password," which are often referred to as a login. This module retrieves user information previously stored in the database and uses the information gained to verify the user. This module is set in place as a security mechanism to prevent malicious individuals from gaining access to the computer.

Figure 4.4 Login page

4.5.4 The Home Page

The diagram in figure 4.5 shows the home page module, this is the main module where most of the actions are carried out, this module can link to other modules such as add vehicle module, manage vehicle and history of vehicle. This module is unique because it contains a grid view of all the slots previously slated in the registration page. It notifies the user of the application when a slot has been occupied by changing to red color. So, users can now at a glance of the homepage that a slot has been occupied. The homepage is designed to be easy on the eyes and also to be user friendly. It is equipped with large buttons for easy identification, it is simplified so that the people who are non-computer savvy can find it easy to use. Our first priority is to make the system usable.

Figure 4.5 Home page

i. Add Vehicle

The diagram in figure 4.6 shows the add vehicle module. In this module vehicles that enter the premises is added to the system by recording their name, mobile, vehicle number and vehicle type which accommodates trucks (16-wheeler) and cars which are 4-wheeler. When the add button is clicked the vehicle is added to the database and a slot is automatically assigned to the vehicle depending on the vehicle type.

Figure 4.6 Add Vehicle

ii. Manage Vehicle

This module is part of the home page, it handles and organizes the vehicles in the parking lot. It records the time the vehicle entered the premises and also records other details of the driver, in this module one can free up lot space when a car exits the premises with the click of the exit button. It has a refresh button to reload the page and view new vehicles that have been added.

Figure 4.7 Manage Vehicle

iii. History

This module allows the admin or user to record all the cars that have ever entered and left the premises. It keeps a record of all the vehicles, it records the entry and exit time. There is a refresh button to reload the page and to view vehicles that just left the premises.

Figure 4.8 History

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 SUMMARY

O-Park is a parking allocation and management application built on PyCharm. It has been developed using the user-oriented approach, python's PyQt makes the user interface basic and easy to interact with.

O-Park is a platform developed to allocate parking slots in the parking lot, it is able to record the time a vehicle enters and leaves a premise. It is built with an easy to use interface so that those who are not computer savvy can operate the system easily.

The software is built for all platforms, such as Windows Mac and Ubuntu. PyCharm is the comprehensive software framework for which O-park is designed. The programming languages used are Python, PyQt5. The database manager was using the SQL command line.

5.2 CONCLUSION

Parking has always been essential since the invention of cars and many solutions have been developed to make the parking solution easier. O-Park is one of those solutions which is guaranteed to make the parking process easier. This was an incredible learning opportunity for me throughout the project. This project has taken me through the different phases of project development and provided me with a genuine insight into application programming. I got an impression of the development industry with the joy of working and excitement involved when dealing with the various challenges and problems.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

This desktop application is regarded as the first version of the implementation as more and more features are proposed for later versions. Some recommendations for the creation of later versions are:

- i. In the first version of O-Park, the vehicles plate number is manually inputted into the system. Future versions could integrate an Optical Character Recognition (OCR) feature to ease the process of capturing vehicle license plates.
- ii. In the first version of O-Park, accommodations were made for four and sixteen-wheeled vehicles. Future versions could make accommodation of two-wheeled vehicles.

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